

EFFECTS OF PROGRESSIVE FRACTURE ON THE BUCKLING RESISTANCE OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of local and regional damage on the load carrying capability and structural behavior of a composite cylindrical shell under external pressure is investigated. An integrated computer code is utilized for the evaluation of composite structural degradation and buckling stability under external pressure. Damage initiation, growth, accumulation, and propagation to structural fracture are included in the simulation. Results identify cases in which local damage has a significant effect on structural collapse under external pressure. Effect of the laminate structure on stability is investigated.

KEYWORDS: Buckling, Composites, Composite Structures, Computational Simulation, Damage, Degradation, Durability, Fracture, Laminates, Pressure, Shells, Stability, Structural Degradation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their high strength, stiffness, and multiplicity of tailoring options for the laminate structure, composite shells are used in many applications. Some composite shells are required to withstand significant levels of external pressure. In general, any accidental damage or fabrication defect is expected to weaken the overall structural strength, durability, and stability. Standard design practice accepts the possibility of local defects and requires structural safety under probable accidental damage. It is therefore useful to quantify the reduction in the overall strength, durability, and stability of a composite shell structure due to existing defects and accidental damage.

Under external pressure composite shells display two types of global failure mode: 1) elastic buckling and 2) stress fracture. Design cases involving low to moderate levels of external pressure are typically satisfied with a sufficiently large radius-to-thickness ratio such that buckling stability is the fundamental design constraint. On the other hand, when very large external

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pressures are to be serviced, the radius-to-thickness ratio becomes small and stress fracture becomes the primary design concern.

For the purpose of the present discussion, the following terminology is used to describe the various stages of degradation in a composite structure: (1) *Initial defect* refers to the accidental damage as well as to the fabrication defect present in the composite structure independent of the application of service loading; (2) *damage initiation* refers to the start of damage induced by service loading; (3) *damage growth* is the progression of damage from the location of damage initiation to adjacent regions; (4) *damage accumulation* is the increase in the amount of damage in the damaged region with additional damage modes becoming active; (5) *damage propagation* is the rapid progression of damage to other regions of the structure; (6) *structural fracture* is the ultimate fracture, disintegration, or collapse of the structure. At any stage of damage progression, if there is a high level of structural resistance to damage propagation under the service loading, the structure is stable with regard to fracture. The corresponding state of structural damage is referred to as *stable damage*. On the other hand, if damage progression does not encounter significant structural resistance, it corresponds to an *unstable damage* state. Unstable damage progression is characterized by very large increases in the amount of damage due to small increases in loading. Whereas during stable damage progression the amount of increase in damage is consistent with the increase in loading.

The behavior of laminated composite structures under loading is rather complex. Because of the numerous possibilities with material combinations, composite geometry, ply orientations, and loading conditions, it is essential to have an effective computational capability to predict the behavior of composite structures for any loading, geometry, composite material combinations, and boundary conditions. In addition to the evaluation of buckling stability, the predictions of damage initiation, growth, accumulation, and propagation to fracture are important in evaluating the load carrying capacity and reliability of composite structures. Quantification of the structural fracture resistance is also required to evaluate the durability/life of composite structures.

The CODSTRAN (COMposite Durability STRuctural ANALysis) computer code [1] has been developed for this purpose. CODSTRAN is able to simulate damage initiation, damage growth, and fracture in composites under various loading and environmental conditions. The simulation of progressive fracture by CODSTRAN has been verified to be in reasonable agreement with experimental data from tensile tests [2]. Recent additions to CODSTRAN have enabled investigation of the effects of composite degradation on structural response and buckling stability [3], composite damage induced by dynamic loading [4], composite structures global fracture toughness [5], effect of the hygrothermal environment on durability [6], damage progression in composite shells subjected to internal pressure [7], an overall evaluation of the progressive fracture in polymer matrix composite structures [8], the durability of stiffened composite shells under load combinations [9], and design considerations for progressive fracture in composite shell structures [10]. The purpose of this paper is to examine the evaluation of buckling stability and durability for a composite shell under external pressure. A full size cylindrical shell is considered under increasing levels of external pressure. Buckling stability is examined with regard to the design of the laminate structure to carry the external pressure. Damage propagation studies identify structural stabilization requirements to assure structural safety.

2. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF CODSTRAN

CODSTRAN is an integrated, open-ended, stand alone computer code consisting of three modules: composite mechanics, finite element analysis, and damage progression modelling. The overall evaluation of composite structural durability is carried out in the damage progression module [1] that keeps track of composite degradation for the entire structure. The damage progression module relies on ICAN [11] for composite micromechanics, macromechanics and laminate analysis, and calls a finite element analysis module that uses anisotropic thick shell elements to model laminated composites and to carry out stress and stability analyses [12].

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the computational simulation cycle in CODSTRAN. The ICAN composite mechanics module is called before and after each finite element analysis. Prior to each finite element analysis, the ICAN module computes the composite properties from the fiber and matrix constituent characteristics and the composite layup. The finite element analysis module accepts the composite properties that are computed by the ICAN module at each node and performs the analysis at each load increment. After an incremental finite element analysis, the computed generalized nodal force resultants and deformations are supplied to the ICAN module that evaluates the nature and amount of local damage, if any, in the plies of the composite laminate. Individual ply failure modes are determined by ICAN using failure criteria associated with the negative and positive limits of the six ply-stress components ($\sigma_{\ell 11}$, $\sigma_{\ell 22}$, $\sigma_{\ell 33}$, $\sigma_{\ell 12}$, $\sigma_{\ell 13}$, $\sigma_{\ell 23}$), a modified distortion energy (MDE) or combined stress failure criterion, and interply delamination due to relative rotation of the plies.

The generalized stress-strain relationships for each node are revised according to the composite damage evaluated by the ICAN module after each finite element analysis. The model is automatically updated with a new finite element mesh/properties, and the structure is reanalyzed for further deformation and damage. If there is no damage after a load increment, the structure is considered to be in equilibrium and an additional load increment is applied. Figure 2 shows a schematic of CODSTRAN damage tracking, expressed in terms of a load-displacement relationship. Point 1 represents the last equilibrium state before initial damage. When the structure is loaded by an additional load increment to point 2, ply failure criteria indicate damage initiation. At this stage CODSTRAN degrades the composite properties affected by the damage and reanalyzes the structure under the same load increment to reach point 3. However, at point 3, composite ply failure criteria indicate additional damage. Accordingly, structural properties are further degraded and analysis is repeated under the same load increment to reach point 4. There is no indication of further damage at point 4, therefore the structure is considered to be in equilibrium. Subsequently, another load increment is applied leading to point 5 with possible damage growth, accumulation, or propagation. The procedure is continued through the stages of damage progression to structural fracture. Simulation is stopped when global structural fracture is predicted by rapid damage propagation.

3. STABILITY UNDER EXTERNAL PRESSURE

The buckling stability of a prototype cylindrical shell is considered. The composite system is made of Thornel-300 graphite fibers in an epoxy matrix (T300/Epoxy). The investigated cylindrical shell has a diameter of 4.572 m (15 ft.) and a length of 15.24 m (50 ft.). The finite element model contains 800 nodes and 768 equal size quadrilateral thick shell elements.

The composite shell is subjected to an external pressure. To simulate the stresses in the walls of a closed-end cylindrical vessel, a uniformly distributed axial compression is applied to the cylinder such that axial compressive stresses in the shell wall are half those developed in the hoop direction. To impose the axial loading, one of the end sections is restrained against axial translation and axial compression is applied uniformly at the opposite end of the shell.

3.1 Effect of Shell Thickness and Composite Structure on Stability: Using a basic composite layup of $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_s$, with 0.127 mm (0.005 in.) plies, three different thicknesses of the shell are investigated via CODSTRAN with respect to buckling stability. Table 1 summarizes the results of this investigation. Figure 3 shows the buckling pressure as a function of the number of plies comprising the shell structure. Figure 3 also shows the fundamental buckling mode of the closed end cylindrical shell having 576 plies with $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s,6}$ composite structure. The corresponding external buckling pressure is 2,323 KPa (337 psi). The first free vibration frequency is 25.6 Hz. The fundamental vibration mode is similar to the first buckling mode except that the vibration mode has four full sinusoidal waves around the circumference of the shell whereas the buckling mode has six.

3.2 Effect of Laminate Structure on Stability: Alternative composite structures are examined via CODSTRAN with regard to buckling stability as summarized in Table 2. Table 2 indicates the significance of composite layup with regard to buckling stability. Of the three cases investigated, the best layup with regard to buckling stability is $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_s$.

4. DAMAGE PROGRESSION AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE

The T300/Epoxy composite system that was investigated with regard to buckling stability is retained to illustrate a typical CODSTRAN durability analysis. The laminate consists of five hundred and seventy-six 0.127 mm (0.005 in.) plies resulting in a composite shell thickness of 73.2 mm (2.88 in.). The laminate configuration is $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s,6}$. The 90° plies are in the hoop direction and the $\pm 15^\circ$ plies are oriented with respect to the axial direction of the shell. The cylindrical shell has a diameter of 4.572 m (15 ft.) and a length of 15.24 m (50 ft.) as it was for the stability investigation. At one point along the circumference, at half-length of the cylinder, initial damage in a number of plies is prescribed. External pressure is applied on the cylindrical vessel with closed ends. The pressure is gradually increased until the shell is fractured, or until the buckling pressure is reached.

For a structure without defects CODSTRAN predicts that outer hoop plies will fracture at 19.5 MPa (2.83 ksi) external pressure if buckling instability is prevented. The 19.5 MPa fracture pressure for a defect free shell is 8.4 times the elastic buckling pressure. Therefore, unless the shell is stiffened against buckling, the design will be controlled by stability considerations. Nevertheless, structural collapse by damage propagation need also be considered due to the possibility of accidental damage. Durability analysis quantifies the reduction in the ultimate external pressure because of accidental mutilation of the composite shell structure.

Figure 4 shows the length of accidental damage by crushing or scraping of the outer 3/4 of the shell thickness along the shell axis and the external pressure at which the damage remains stable. The damaged length shown on the horizontal axis in Figure 4 is normalized with respect to the total length of the cylindrical shell. Damage stability in the pressure range of 0.69 to 2.32 MPa (100 to 337 psi) is depicted; where the 2.32 MPa upper limit corresponds to the buckling

pressure. Information presented in Figure 4 is useful for the design of required framework spacing to assure structural integrity in case of accidental damage.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the light of the durability investigation of the example composite shell and from the general perspective of the available computer code the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Computational simulation, with the use of established composite mechanics and finite element modules, can be used to predict the influence of existing ply defects and accidental damage, as well as loading, on the safety and durability of composite structures.
2. For thick shells under external pressure the ultimate structural fracture pressure is not sensitive to the location and the existence of minor defects.
3. The demonstrated procedure is flexible and applicable to all types of constituent materials, structural geometry, and loading. Hybrid composites and homogeneous materials, as well as binary composites can be simulated.
4. The reduction in the ultimate load and the variation of the structural fracture mode are predictable with reference to the location and size of defects/accidental damage.
5. Fracture toughness parameters such as the damage initiation load and the structural fracture load are identifiable for any structure by the demonstrated method.
6. The CODSTRAN methodology delineates a new global approach to structural integrity assessment.

Acknowledgment—The participation of the first author in this research was sponsored by NASA-Lewis Research Center under grant NAG-3-1101, monitored by Dr. P. L. N. Murthy. Some of the computational simulations were carried out by Mr. James M. Rivers, Research Assistant.

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Figure 1 CODSTRAN Simulation Cycle

Figure 2 CODSTRAN Damage Tracking

Table 1: Effect of Shell Thickness on Stability

Number of Plies	Shell Thickness (mm)	Composite Structure (T300/Epoxy)	Buckling Pressure (KPa)
144	18.3	$[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s4}$	73.8
288	36.6	$[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s5}$	392
576	73.2	$[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s6}$	2,323

Conversion Factor: 1 KPa = 0.14504 psi

Table 2: Effect of Composite Structure on Stability

Number of Plies	Shell Thickness (mm)	Composite Structure (T300/Epoxy)	Buckling Pressure (KPa)
576	73.2	$[\pm 15/\mp 15/90/\pm 15/\mp 15]_{s6}$	1,087
576	73.2	$[\pm 45/\mp 45/90/\pm 45/\mp 45]_{s6}$	1,608
576	73.2	$[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_{s6}$	2,323

Conversion Factor: 1 KPa = 0.14504 psi

Figure 3 Buckling under External Pressure T300/Epoxy Composite Shell $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_s$

Figure 4 Damage Tolerance under Pressure T300/Epoxy Composite Shell 576 Plies: $[90_2/\pm 15/90_2/\mp 15/90]_s$